

Coping Strategies For Survivors Of Violence During The Covid-19 Crisis And Its Relationship To Mental Health

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Abstract:

The research dealt with the study of the adaptation of violence against women during the covid-19 crisis, as it is one of the most dangerous practices witnessed by many Arab countries, as violence against women has its health and psychological harms, as violence is practiced by both partners and parents, and the mechanism of adaptation strategies for survivors of psychological and health violence, is in finding appropriate solutions for survivors of targeted violence, especially during crises such as the covid crisis.

Violence and its relationship in the covid-19 crisis and its effects on mental health the problem was what coping strategies for violence for survivors of violence during the covid-19 crisis and their relationship to mental health.

Key words: violence, mental health, covid 19.

The research problem

The family is exposed to many of the problems it faces, perhaps the most prominent of these problems is related to violence, and the appearance of signs of aversion and boredom between spouses, to a degree where the relationship is limited to keeping dealing with some formal matters, according to data and statements issued by government agencies and civil society organizations

It is noticeable in the percentage of cases of violence, which has become a phenomenon that is spreading day by day. Experience has shown that when a woman is responsible for buying and cooking food for the family, food insecurity increases as a result of crises, which puts her at increased risk, for example, she may be exposed to intimate partner violence and other forms of domestic violence due to increased tensions in the household. In addition, life-saving care and support for survivors of violence, such as clinical

management of rape cases, mental health, and psychosocial support in comprehensive crisis centers in specialized hospitals, may be disrupted when health service providers are overloaded and busy dealing with covid-19 cases and how to adapt to survivors, the problem of the study can be identified by answering (what coping strategies for violence for survivors of violence during the covid-19 crisis and their relationship with mental health).

The importance of research

The phenomenon of family violence has become more and more aggravated in our modern life, and many families and families are suffering from the repercussions of family violence, and the resulting negatives threaten the family entity with disintegration, weakness and collapse, which in turn negatively reflects on the integrity of the social structure. Despite all the changes that have occurred to the family in modern societies, which have greatly influenced its Form, role and social and cultural functions, the existing relations within the family are still associated with the traditional power building, which is based on the superiority of men and his economic control in society and the family in particular, that

A building that is supported and consecrated through values, culture and religion, which has made many women's memories not only at the level of Arab societies, but also at the world level, an unhappy day, due to its continuity and the increase of many practices that are still prevalent and practiced against women, foremost of which is violence, discrimination and inequality, despite the existence of many international conventions, charters and declarations affirming the human rights of women (Shawki, 1992: 8).

The World Health Organization reports that violence against women is an undue burden on health-care systems, as it seems that women who suffer from violence need health-care services at a much higher cost compared to women who have not been subjected to violence .

Several studies have also linked the mistreatment of women with the level of violence internationally, as these studies have shown that the best prediction of violence at the international level is related to the extent of mistreatment of women in society. And we find there are figures recorded in violence against women in many countries:-

In France, about (95%) of the victims of violence are women, and (51%) of them as a result of being beaten by their husbands or family members. In Canada, we find that about (60%) of men practice violence against their wives, and in India, we note that (8) out of every (10) women are victims of violence, whether domestic violence or murder. In Peru, we note that about (70%) of crimes recorded by the police are against women, and in the United States of America we find that beatings and physical assault were the main causes of serious injuries to women (Azizi, 2013: 3).

For this reason, the phenomenon of violence against women has recently received great attention at the Arab and international levels; at the theoretical research levels, especially in the field of psychological studies, violence against women has multiple forms, and that one of the most common forms of violence (physical – verbal – insult), and interest in studying this phenomenon has increased in the seventies and Eighties of the twentieth century, as this period of time witnessed the first study of the prevalence of marital violence in the United States of America, and also witnessed the emergence of many periodicals specializing in the publication of studies on family violence (Ahmed, the 2012: 433-434).

Research objectives:

Identify the strategy of adaptation and violence directed at women.

Violence and its relationship in the covid-19 crisis and its effects on mental health.

Methodology

The descriptive-analytical approach was followed.

Definition of terms

Strategic Adaptation: the ability of adaptive couples to adapt despite the existence of odd problems with them, and to know the means to control them as much as possible (Tamimi: walkhshali, 2115).

Procedural definition adaptation strategy: it is the wife's adaptation to family problems, pressures and family violence by parents and husband for the continuation of life

Violence: there are many terms that revolve around violence, including legal, psychological, and social.

Violence is defined from a social perspective as the intentional use of force or coercion against others, usually resulting in destruction or infliction of physical or non-physical harm and harm to oneself or others (Abu Al-Nasr, 2008, 7).

It is any act committed against a woman that results or is likely to result in psychological, physical, financial or sexual harm or suffering to a woman, including threats to commit such an act, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of Liberty (Al-badania, 2004, 8).

Procedural definition violence: every abuse received by a woman by parents, husband, family in the form of verbal, physical, social, economic violence leaves a psychological and health impact on women's behavior

Covid-19: the procedural definition is a global pandemic that has affected the world, resulting in significant deaths among the world and leaving psychological and health effects for the family and women in particular .

Survivor of violence: a person who has been subjected to violence and his terms "victim" and "survivor" can be used interchangeably. "Victim" is a term commonly used in the legal and medical sectors. "Survivor" is the term generally preferred in the psychosocial support sectors because it means resilience.

Survivors should create a supportive environment to safeguard the rights of the survivor, ensure her safety and treat her with dignity and respect. This approach aims to help the survivor recover and strengthen her (or his) ability to know and express her needs and desires; this approach emphasizes that the survivor makes decisions about the interventions that she can get". Reducing risks, strengthening resilience and assisting recovery (Inter-Agency Standing Committee, 2015).

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Adaptation strategy: Some couples are trying to adapt to reduce violence to its negative effects within the family.

To preserve the interests of the children. The fields of psychology have contributed to the explanation of individual behavior.

However, it has its origin in adapting to many demands and necessities that put pressure on it, as some couples seek through this adaptation process to maintain a balance between their various psychological and social needs and to achieve the process of marital adjustment strategy, many couples resort to following some of the marital adjustment strategies, which are cognitive methods used by individuals to assess tensions. For example, a problem-solving strategy for negative situations is a kind of adaptive strategy that ensures the search for information, obtaining social support from others (Bailey & Smith, 2003).

Psychological and social adaptation is a positive condition found in humans, as it indicates that they enjoy a number of manifestations that boil down to a carefree life, the manifestations of which include self-satisfaction, a sense of happiness and optimism, a tendency to fun and patience, and enjoying life. It is an indicator of psychological adaptation that happiness and optimism, a tendency to fun and patience, enjoyment of life . One of the indicators of psychological adaptation is that the spouses ' outlook on life is realistic, that their ambitions match the level of their potential, and that they have a set of characteristics, such as emotional stability, social responsibility and flexibility, and that one of the spouses has a set of positive attitudes, standards and values, such as respect, and performance of Duty (Al-Jaid: 2001, 23).

A flexible person responds appropriately to the environment in order to achieve adaptation, and the less flexibility he has, the less his ability to adapt. If one of the spouses wants to adapt to life, he must familiarize himself with ways to solve problems, familiarize himself with all their aspects, know ways to face them, and acquire the necessary skill to deal with them. Adaptation is that activity that an individual exerts to remove any tension that may occur with him and to maintain his internal and external balance. frenerig 1997 and Taylor 1996 point out that individuals with high scores in measures of psychological toughness, use more effective coping strategies compared to individuals

Who receive low scores in psychological hardness (key : 2010, 45).

Marital adaptation is a natural outcome of the nature of interactions between spouses, in many emotional, social, cultural, and economic aspects, which consists in expressing the emotional feelings of the other party, and notifying him of respect and trust, and indicates marital adaptation through the emotional maturity of the spouses that enables them to face problems in a constructive way (Ali: 2013, 34).

We find that most of the couple's behavior is only attempts to achieve psychological adaptation, while the manifestations of maladaptation are represented as an expression of poor compatibility between them.

In the same context, we find that the lack of compatibility and bilateral cohesion between spouses is one of the most prominent reasons leading to discord and abandonment, whether through the official announcement of divorce, or from or silencing the marriage and constant violence (Faya, et al., 2013).

Violence against women:

The concept of violence against women:- the Violence against the woman

Linguistically, violence is defined by Ibn Manzoor as breaking an order and not being gentle with it, which is against being gentle with something, and I am very violent, i.e. taking it and blaming it, and violence is beating " (Ibn Manzoor, 1956: 276)

The definition of the concept of violence in social studies and in linguistic Dictionaries on its combination with force and excess in its use, the Larus lacrosse lexicon referred to violence as a characteristic of everything that results in an action with extreme and brutal force, i.e. violence, especially for what is aggressive inside a person, and then an expression of the utmost severity of practice, it is transcended through speech and behavior. The Encyclopedia universals referred to violence as an act practiced by an individual or individuals against an individual or other individuals through violence in Word and deed (Najat Al-Razi violence against women: (www.Pikrwanakh.aljabriab Al-qabaa (2004) developed a sociological definition of violence that violence is the use of severity and cruelty in the environment of human beings, and this explains that, violent behavior is that behavior issued by a human directed against another human, whether male or female, a boy or a child, it is an emotional behavior issued by one person directed towards another person (al-qabaa: 2008: 23).

(Violence is defined :- according to the definition provided in the WHO World Report on violence and Health (WHO/2000), violence is the intentional use of physical force by threat or actual practice against oneself or another person, group or society, which results in harm, injury, deprivation, harm, death, psychological damage or ... Violence includes all forms of violence, physical and mental neglect, harm and abuse suffered by women (www.sy.gov.reefnet)

Violence patterns against women

Violence is divided into two main groups according to who commits the act of violence.

And this has made a difference

Classification between violence that affects the person himself, and violence that is caused by another person or a small group of people, or by the action of larger groups such as states, organized political groups, or unorganized military groups. the following are the different types of violence faced by women:

First of all. Self-directed violence

Self-directed violence is divided into:

* Suicidal behavior: includes suicidal thoughts and suicide attempts.

* Self-violation: includes self-mutilation: it is a destructive behavior with the intention of a woman harming herself physically or psychologically, feeling depressed and hopeless. And the unwillingness to live through contemplative thoughts by the process of suicide...That this pattern stems from the state of frustration as a result of subconscious psychological conflicts that afflict women and hinder them from achieving their goals, and therefore women tend to self-abuse to vent the latent forces of frustration.

Secondly. Violence directed by others: it is divided into:

* Domestic (family) violence: it is violence that occurs largely between family members and close relatives of the individual and usually occurs at home. Violence against women within the family extends throughout its life cycle from prenatal violence to violence against her as an elderly woman:

(A) violence between partners: or as it is referred to as domestic violence or abuse between spouses, especially from husband to wife. It proved to be the most widespread of all forms of violence against women. It includes the following forms:

Physical violence: which includes the use of physical force, physical force or a weapon with the intent to harm or injure a woman.

Sexual violence: which includes sexual intercourse in the form of assault without the consent of women - both married and unmarried.

Psychological violence: which consists in controlling, isolating, humiliating or embarrassing a woman.

Economic violence: it consists in depriving women of access to and control over basic resources.

(B) harmful traditional practices: sex selection, early marriage, dowry-related violence, female genital mutilation, crimes committed in the name of honour, abuse of widows, including pushing them to commit suicide (Bitar: bit: 12).

* **Community violence:**

1-it is any behavior or act characterized by aggression, issued by a party that may be an individual in society, a group or a social class, with the aim of exploiting or subjugating a woman in an unequal relationship, causing material, moral or psychological damage to her.

2. it is the violence that occurs between individuals who are not related to each other and may or may not know each other, and generally occurs outside the home, such as the violence that women face in transport, in workplaces, in schools, sports clubs, colleges, hospitals and other social institutions and is often called sexual harassment.

3-it constitutes a great pressure and burden on the family, which pushes them to the so-called honor crimes, washing shame, and exerting pressure on girls for multiple purposes. It takes the form of physical, sexual, psychological and economic violence.

(A) sexual violence committed by a person other than the spouse (relative, friend, man known to the woman, neighbor, co-worker, stranger) it is difficult to determine the extent of the prevalence of this type of violence because in many societies sexual violence remains an issue that brings great shame to the woman and her family, and statistics from police records are unreliable due to the underreporting of such crimes.

(B) trafficking in women: which is violence against women that occurs in a variety of situations, especially the poor, with low education, often involving different actors, including:

- Families.
- Local brokers,
- International criminal networks.
- And the immigration authorities.

Trafficking occurs between one country and another or within the same country. Women and children are mostly trafficked for sexual exploitation. It also includes the recruitment, transportation, sheltering or reception of persons by the threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, kidnapping, fraud, deception, abuse of power, exploitation of a vulnerable situation, giving or receiving payments or benefits to obtain the consent of a person who has control over another person for the purpose of exploitation.

(C) violence against women and multiple forms of discrimination related to social and cultural norms and the orientations of each social, economic or political system. factors such as a woman's race, class, class, being a migrant or a refugee, her age, religion, marital status, being disabled or HIV-positive, all affect the form of the degree of violence to which she is subjected and the way it is practiced against her. it increases the less chance an individual (woman) has of reaching her basic human rights (Tantawi: 2005: 43).

Factors (causes) of violence against women:

With the persistence of elements of the prevailing patriarchal culture and the low level of education, the tendencies of men to practice violence against women increase, in addition

to the lack of awareness of rights and duties, the continuation of repression or political marginalization and other political, economic and cultural conditions that encouraged the practice of violence and the weak ability to resist it.

In general, the factors of violence against women can be classified into:

1. Social factors: Violence against women is a complex phenomenon inherent in a society based on beliefs, traditions and social customs that encourage and reinforce male power, and the rapid developments that have occurred in Iraqi society have had a clear impact on the implantation of new behavioral patterns that have negative aspects, in that Iraqi society contains a traditional construction based on male superiority and female inferiority, the collapse of social and vulnerability) which contribute to the study of family violence And usually the one who owns the largest share of resources is the adult male, and the prevailing customs and traditions in society impose on its members certain behavioral models that make physical strength very important, boys learn that they must be strong because strength is one of the measures of masculinity, while girls learn to be thin, beautiful and weak, in other words socialization plays an important role in completely different personality

Marital disputes and conflict between spouses, such as marriage with another or the desire to separate and take revenge, also play a role in contributing to violence against women, and marriage without the consent of the parents, which makes the girl lose the expected protection from her parents in case she is subjected to violence (Al-Sarai: 2004, 16).

2. Cultural factors: One of the most factors that play a role in explaining violence against women is cultural factors, the prevailing culture recognizes only the role of the girl as a wife or housewife, and allows her to study and work, this is in order to improve her chances of marriage and that this situation is not exposed to her main role in the service of the husband and the care of the children, but if the age of marriage is late, or she married and did not have children, or married and gave birth to females, divorced or widowed, all this makes her the object of pity from members of society, regardless of what professional status she has achieved or during the man under the family and marriage system, the cultural structure of women's rights is generally wasted She is despised, and it is a manifestation of contempt for women that it becomes one of the most heinous accusations against a man that he is a woman, and a stain may remain on his forehead in some incident. Folk Proverbs reflect the status and status of the woman's body, which is consistent with society's view of women as a special pleasure or pleasure, not an entity for her moral and human existence.folk heritage is one of the general tributaries in determining the structure of the prevailing culture, which carries a lot of implications that enshrine values and standards that call for the oppression of women and limiting their status in the Family.

popular examples are many, and belief in superstition, magic and the like, which increases suspicion and raises the likelihood of violence.

3. Economic factors: economic factors are the most important factors of domestic violence in general and violence against women in particular, as most researchers in the field of violence against women point out that the abuse suffered by women is due to many factors, including poverty, unemployment, lack of income, frustrations and economic crises, and they state that violence against women, including rape, comes as a result of poverty and deprivation (: 1997, p.119), the rates of violence are high in societies where there is no proper sharing of their wealth and there is a disparity between incomes to a large extent, unequal opportunities and socio-economic disparities, economic factors are represented by low rates of economic growth with high population growth rates, where the share of GDP per capita is low, especially with a large disparity in the distribution of wealth, which leads to unemployment of men, especially if he is the sole breadwinner of the family, and women who do not work are more exposed to violence.

Unemployment can cause a husband to feel that he is not a man, due to his inability to
The relationship between poverty and violence against women is an interactive relationship, as it goes in a circular complex of causality, poverty can be a key factor in violence against women and vice versa, we find, for example, violence practiced against women and its relationship to poverty through trafficking in women

(Prostitution) in eastern Europe and the conditions of females at work in Pakistan and carpet factories in

Nepal (age: 201: 186) thus, violence against women is a major factor in women's poverty and poverty in general, and to illustrate this idea we can explain it from three levels: the individual, the home and society. For women, Violence Against Women and economic dependence interact in an evil circle. violence helps to deepen women's economic dependence on men, and this is what makes them unable to resist this violence. at the domestic level, violence against women restricts their choices and limits their production, and all this weakens the health of women and the health of their children. poverty at the domestic level has more consequences if we look beyond the Will and the home and move more on society, where we find that violence against women hinders opportunities for social, economic and Human Development.

4. Political factors: The political factors were represented by the low representation of women in decision-making centers such as the political and judicial authorities and the media, which prevents them from influencing their own decisions, including those related to the treatment of domestic violence and violence against wives, and the weakness of women's political organizations affected to exert pressure on government and judicial authorities to make appropriate decisions to improve the situation of women and remove

injustice from them, in addition, there is a lack of adequate and parallel attention by the political authorities to issues of domestic violence, and then a lack of awareness of human rights, including women's rights, and this lack of awareness includes both men and women, but women are usually less aware of it due to the low the level Most women are confined to the home without going out to work or to participate in political and public life.

5. Legal factors: A number of factors related to laws play varying roles in the spread of domestic violence, including laws that discriminate between men and women, such as custody rights, maintenance, health and social guarantees, etc., and the lack of knowledge of the laws by women in a wide range of them, which makes women consider the practice of violence by men against them is normal or at least can not or sexual harassment, for example) and finally The reluctance to deal with the security authorities regarding the problems of domestic violence and considering such problems as family issues in which other parties may not intervene.

Negative effects of violence against women

First / health effects:

Violence against women affects the health of women and their children in a direct and indirect way, health is a key factor in material poverty and more broadly in human poverty. in a previous study, violence against women causes illness and disability among women in the ages ranging from (15-44), compared to deaths that occur as a result of malaria, cancer, traffic accidents and wars (Shawki: 365, 200) in addition, violence against women is a direct cause of harm, ill health and death, violence against women and so on affects her health in indirect ways, for example unwanted pregnancy the health risks that this carries arise as a result of the rape. Other effects include the transmission of diseases through sexual practices such as hepatitis and AIDS, and that the practice of abuse over the years against women negatively affects women and causes them to have health problems for some women, the burden of abuse is too great to allow them to lead a normal life. domestic violence may have been one of the causes that lead to depression and suicide (Geradin: 64). violence against women is also a major factor in child mortality, because a woman who is beaten may lose the fetus as a result of abortion, stillbirth or the birth of an immature child.

II / economic effects:

The negative health consequences of violence against women in many cases lead us to bad economic results for women, and this is what shows us the low productivity of women, and one of the effects of

The economic cause for women is domestic violence, for example, which may force a woman to leave the house and go to low-paid jobs in order to live. On the other hand, violence against women can prevent women from working outside the home, and this can

take the form of sexual harassment of women in markets, streets or even in workplaces, and this is what the International Labor Organization pointed out in 1999 that many women discovered that there is no safety to work in the field of selling in markets, or to practice any economic activity outside the home for fear of violence against them, Violence Against Women reinforces their exclusion and isolation from their society, and in other circumstances, violence against women may prevent women from controlling their personal needs, in South Asia, women are prevented from retain their inherited material rights such as land or be forced to cede About a man for fear of being threatened by male family members for example husbands or brothers (slave: 2008, 57) we can say that thinking about violence against women in the light of socio-economic conditions shows us its impact on all sectors of society, and not only on women, who are the first victims of this phenomenon, direct public costs include expenses directly related to violence, medical treatment, psychological counseling, criminal justice services, providing housing for women and their children, as for indirect costs as a result of violence against women, for example, women's low participation in the labor market, low income and absenteeism, and therefore a decrease in spending and demand for economic goods, in addition to what this violence affects human development, men who harm women It weakens the human capital of the nations that depend on it and thus endangers human development, and it can also be said that when individuals are unable to satisfy their needs, the state collapses socially and economically.

III / social effects:

Family violence always becomes linked to social violence.the continuation of violence from generation to generation affects the use of violence and the exercise of force on others, whether inside or outside the home. for girls who are exposed to family violence in childhood, they will be more receptive to violence from their parents, and therefore from their husbands when they grow up, and so on. boys who practice violence against their mothers, this is a start for them. in both cases, the circle is connected.

Violence against women also restricts their authority and status and hinders social progress, and even deprives girls of education, because when violence spreads, it will prevent them from going to school and hinder their good performance in school because of the fear of parents for their female children while they are going to school.the Iraqi scene witnessed this in the periods of democratic transition after 2003 in some areas of Baghdad and the hotspots of Ramadi, Ninawa and Salah al-Din, especially during the ISIS period in 2014. Violence may be an alarm bell that indicates the failure of the family in the process of socialization entrusted to it and a sign of the existence of some imbalances that must be paid attention to to fix them in the structure of the family, building strength in it and the nature of relationships within it, and therefore identifying the causes leading to its

occurrence would put our hands on the factors of personal and societal stability, as well as help decision makers to adopt policies to deal with it effectively, and this is what Durkheim pointed out in his theory (al-Rabeei: 61, D.C).

Factors leading to violence against women-beliefs and facts about violence against women

Violence can be traced back to the following reasons:

1-negative values: which do not see the true and full eligibility of women as a full human being, a right and a duty.. This is what establishes a life based on marginalization and contempt for women.

2-the general cultural backwardness and the resulting ignorance of the components of civilization and human development that must rise on the shoulders of both women and men within the equation of integration between them to make a meaningful and advanced life.

3-wrong social traditions and customs that prevent the growth of women's role and creativity to unite life with the elements of Renaissance.

4-the weight of suffocating economic crises and the resulting public violence due to inflation, poverty, unemployment and need, and the economic factor occupies 45% of cases of violence against women.

5-negative effects resulting from environmental problems that put pressure on humans.

6-the weakness of women themselves in demanding their human and national rights and working to activate and grow their social, political and economic role.

7-the bad employment of power, whether within the family, social class or the state, as it is based on condescension and crushing the rights of the weakest within these societal frameworks (Haya Eid Allah 2014, 45).

8-the consequences of catastrophic wars and the culture of violence they create, the prevalence of murder and the violation of human rights, and the devastating results they produce for the economy, security, cohesion and social peace.

9-political tyranny prevents the development of society as a whole, which stands as a stumbling block to

The modern construction of the state, power, citizenship and the supremacy of the culture of human rights.

10-the absence of democracy, including the rule of law, institutions, pluralism, respect and acceptance

The other one.. As a culture and a mechanism governing society and the state so that it is able to respect, develop and protect its citizens (Abdulaziz: 2010: pp. 12_14)

Covid-19 and mental health

The covid-19 pandemic has arrived

The rates of violence have increased at an unprecedented rate in all Arab countries and in countries suffering from economic and political crises by a factor of two. In the Arab countries, the deterioration of Economic, living and social conditions has led to the growing phenomenon of violence in society in general and violence against women of various social and educational levels in particular .

In 2020, complaints of domestic violence doubled by almost 100%, and there were (5) Crimes Against Women, (3) of whom were killed in just two weeks in the same year.⁴⁸ the high rates of violence against women and children coincided with:

(A) the general lockdown measures and the accompanying increased rates of tension amid fears of loss

The lack of social protection networks, the lack of social, legal, security and health support services for women, (b) social distancing measures that have increased the likelihood of violence against the most vulnerable in the family, especially in light of the fact that family members have to stay all victims of supportive frameworks such as family, relatives and friends at home, in conjunction with economic difficulties and loss

(D) increased burdens of care, education, job management and fear of the future

(C) moving away from home isolation in light of the closure of schools and working from home

(H) the abuse by violators of the restrictions placed on the freedom of movement and movement of individuals during the spread of the epidemic, by limiting victims ' access to psychological assistance such as family support through formal and informal networks.

It is no secret that these factors have intensified and their consequences have multiplied with the decline of legal and judicial frameworks dedicated to the protection of women and victims of domestic violence in general, such as hotlines, legal aid, the provision of shelters, family crisis management centers and other mechanisms that used to restrain or reduce the rates of violence, from the psychological and physical the epidemic. Even if it continues, telephone/electronic communication with support and protection counselors often leads to retaliatory behavior by the abuser and then multiply the violence and psychological and physical damage to the victims, which means that the mechanisms of these systems need to be developed to cope with the conditions of domestic violence free of the pandemic .The United Nations describes this growing violence as a shadow pandemic parallel to the corona pandemic, as the stress caused by covid-19 in the health services sector, in turn, caused parallel stress in the basic services sector, such as domestic violence shelters and victim helplines. The pandemic has resulted in an increase in The number of cases of violence against women in the region, coupled with the disruption of basic services for survivors of violence due to lockdown measures. Courts have been closed and a number of procedures related to legal compensation, custody and alimony

issues have been suspended in the context of covid-19-35% of women's civil society organizations indicate that during the pandemic it was easier to access informal or traditional justice mechanisms such as community mediation, or Alternative Dispute Resolution through family or leaders 123. Official statistics of the Iraqi Ministry of Interior indicate the documentation of more than 5 thousand cases of family violence throughout the country during the first half of this year

<https://www.bbc.com/arabic/interactivity-55060915>.

Conclusions :-

- * The percentage of violence among women during the covid-19 crisis has increased very significantly
- * Through the literature and the above, violence is not determined by a specific time, place or environment
- * The social heritage of family education in highlighting the masculine role and its control over women and its control over their fate has a role in the practice of violence
- * The most severe type of domestic violence affecting women is the prevalence of the phenomenon of divorce .
- * That education makes women aware of the reality of their rights and duties
- * Education has a role in building a woman's personality and becoming a leader in her work and home
- * An educated woman is able to rely on herself to practice the requirements of her daily life.

Recommendations:

1-confronting the phenomenon of violence against women through special campaigns and in cooperation with international organizations such as UNICEF, which aims to renounce inherited customs and traditions such as early marriage and holding discussion groups among specialists to raise awareness of mothers, fathers and young people of the danger of these customs and their negative effects on society.

2-paying attention to women's affairs through the national plan adopted by the state to reduce the qualitative gap between men and women, on the premise that reducing the existing discrimination against women leads in practice to reducing the violence against them.

3-providing comprehensive medical aid to women victims of violence and torture by non-governmental organizations and holding seminars, conferences and workshops dealing with the phenomenon of violence against women.

4-seeking to shelter women who are disabled by their parents and husbands in shelters under the supervision of state government institutions that receive women during crises or routine situations.

5. closures, quarantines and other such measures should always be carried out. To contain and combat the spread of the covid-19 virus, in full accordance with human rights standards and in a way that is necessary and proportionate to the risks being assessed - but even when they are, they may have serious repercussions on the lives of people, especially battered women.

6. primary and secondary health care facilities may be required to take cases of survivors of gender-based violence, and to make referrals to specialized hospitals only when a higher level of care is required. Violence referral pathways should also be updated to reflect specialist care facilities.

7. psychosocial support should be available to women and girls who may be affected by the outbreak of the epidemic, and who may also be survivors of gender-based violence. With regard to the previous point-those who may be affected - either directly or indirectly by the outbreak of an infectious disease-the experience can be just as traumatic as the experience of gender-based violence. Recognizing that these two things may co-occur for some women and girls is very important and requires that psychosocial support be available to women and girls, and also available in general.

8-appointing social workers and psychologists in the courts related to family issues in terms of conducting periodic studies on family issues in the courts and coordinating with the authorities related to the issue of domestic violence and follow-up if necessary, and so on in the Ministry of health as well as police stations and other security agencies and the Ministry of Education.

9-establishing psychological and social counseling centers in cities and villages and providing shelters and family protection from violence.

10-encouraging the conduct of research and studies related to violence

11-develop a media plan to shed light on the problems related to domestic violence and educate women on ways to protect themselves from that violence, and encourage them to disclose the violence against them if it occurs, especially when it is severe and harmful or affecting her personality and psychological composition, and the media campaign should aim to alleviate women's feelings of shame, embarrassment or fear of revealing the truth to the authorities dealing with the problem

Proposals:

Conducting a field study of cases of physical and psychological violence, and then preparing a training program for their adaptation in society. there are health and Counseling Centers for the treatment of cases of domestic violence in all governorates managed by a specialist.attention is paid to the media side for women and sensitizing them to distinguish between types of violence and their health and psychological patterns.

References

- 1-Abu Al-Nasr Medhat: the phenomenon of violence in society, Cairo: International Publishing and distribution house 2009.
- 2-Ahmed, Mamdouh saber: forms of domestic violence directed against women and its relationship with some Self-affirmation skills in marital relations, international specialized pedagogical Journal, Volume (1), issue (8), Riyadh, 2012.
- 3-Ahmed Hassan Abdullah Al-Rubaie: criminal justice and social deviation, unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Baghdad / Faculty of Arts-Department of sociology 2012
- 4-Tamimi, Iyad Fadel and al-Khashali, Shaker Jarallah: the impact of the elements of strategic training, 2015 in achieving strategic success: an applied study in commercial banks operating in Jordan .
Jordanian Journal of Business Administration, 2011
- 5-Jalil Wadie mashkour: violence and crime, Arab House of Sciences, Beirut, 1997
- 6-Al-Jaid, Mohammed emotional intelligence and its relationship to psychological and social adaptation among university students unpublished letter Jordan, 2011
- 7-inter-agency Standing Committee guidelines for integrating gender-based violence in humanitarian action: Food Security and agriculture, 2015egypt
- 8-Salem sari and Khader Zakaria, current community problems, al-Ahari printing, publishing and distribution, Damascus, 2004.
- 9-Shawky, the funny violence in the Egyptian Family (second report) exploratory study, National Center for criminal Research, Cairo, 1992
- 10-Tantawi Amal and others: Violence Against Women in Bahrain Center for studies And research 2007
- 11-Aziz, Khadija: violence against women, gender Magazine, Issue(5), women's issues section, Iraq 2013.
- 12-Abdelaziz Abla: violence against women and the protection prescribed to confront it in Islamic law, 2005
- 13-Maan Khalil Omar: sociology of violence, Dar Al Shorouk, Amman, 2010
- 14-Hany Khamis Ahmed Abdel: sociology of crime and delinquency, University Knowledge House, Alexandria, 2008
- 15-Al-Aqeel, Haya Abdullah: violence against women during wars and armed conflicts A field study of Syrian refugee women in Zaatari Camp, Master Thesis, University of Jordan, Amman, Jordan, 2014.
- 16-Iraq: UNFPA Iraq Office Central Bureau of Statistics Jamil, Asma, and others: Violence Against Women in Iraq problems and options 2013

17-Ali, craving for emotional intelligence and its relationship to marital adjustment, (unpublished master's thesis), Faculty of educational and psychological sciences, Amman Arab University, Jordan. 2013

18 - International Institute for women's solidarity: safety and security, elimination of violence against women and girls in Islamic societies, Oman. 2003.

19- Baily A. and Smith, S. (2003). Providing effective coping strategies and support of families with children with Disabilities. *Intervention in School & Clin* 35(5), 294-297.

20- Faye, A, Kalra, G, Subramanyam, A, Shah, H, Kamath, R and Pakhare, A. (2013) Study of Marital Adjustment, Mechanisms of Coping And Psychopathology In Couples Seeking Divorce In India, *Sexual And Relati* 259-271. onship Therapy.